

The Essence of Existentialism in Franz Kafka's *The Metamorphosis*

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Abstract:

A close study of Franz Kafka's *The Metamorphosis* reveals numerous allegorical meanings behind this novella. From being the sole provider of his house, Gregor Samsa meets his massive fall when he transforms into an insect one morning. The existential themes of Kafka's work indicate a greater cycle of arbitrary power in the hands of an authoritative system. This system has taken over both the professional as well as personal world of human beings. *The Metamorphosis* presents the effects of a human existential crisis in the world. Kafka explores the intrinsic aspects of human life by using absurd transformations. Individualism, absurdity, alienation and guilt are some of the major characteristics of existentialism. This paper will focus on these tenets of Existentialism in Franz Kafka's *The Metamorphosis*.

Introduction:

The Metamorphosis chronicles the extensive notions of Existentialism, which is a philosophical theory that focuses on the individual existence of human beings. This existence occurs in an irrational world as the individual strives to find their way. The novella, *The Metamorphosis* is written by Franz Kafka and is published in 1915. The novella centres on the journey of its protagonist Gregor Samsa who transforms into an insect overnight. The reason behind Samsa's metamorphosis is never disclosed however, the story progresses as Samsa tries to get used to his present condition. The novella is widely acclaimed and is said to be Kafka's most famous works. Franz Kafka shares a complicated yet enriched relationship with Existentialism. His work contains the major tenets of Existentialism such as guilt, anxiety, meaninglessness, alienation and the absurd. *The Metamorphosis* is a story about the treachery of family and the terrifying power of arbitrary authority with an indignant perception of oneself.

The absurd world of Franz Kafka:

Kafka's works use the notion of meaninglessness as its premise and make it a point to assert the absurdity of life. Kafka's world is very similar to the real one where we feel incapable of proving our worth in front of authority. This world is a never-ending nightmare where several of us have ended up, even if it is for a moment. The condition of human beings in Kafka's world is unpleasant, depressing and hopeless. In fact, it is way beyond depressing and hopeless. Kafka believes the human race to be the product of "God's bad days". He has rendered our existence to have no purpose except to suffer. We are merely doomed to exist in a world we never asked to be

born in, only to live a meaningless life. This concept is predominantly visible in *The Metamorphosis*. Despite turning into a “vermin”, Gregor Samsa is more concerned with going to work on time. He wants to fulfil his responsibility of relieving his parents of their debt and sending his sister to study at the Conservatorium. The protagonist is not in control of his metamorphosis which demonstrates our inability to have control over our life. According to Jean-Paul Sartre’s Existentialism is a Humanism, “Man is nothing else but that which he makes of himself”. (Paul-Sartre, 1946). A man’s existence is dependent on no one else but him. The existential philosophy believes humans to be thrown into a world where they have to find their purpose. This purpose isn’t pre-determined by God or any other supernatural being, instead, it is up to the individual to discover their worth and assert themselves in a world of challenges. Likewise, Kafka’s writing is emblematic of the journey of self-realization where an individual gets the chance to discover their purpose.

The story works in two worlds- one is fictitious whilst the other is real. In *The Metamorphosis*, these two worlds exist in and outside of Gregor Samsa’s room. Samsa enters the realm of the absurd once he turns into an insect. On the other hand, his family’s financial support has been taken away which leaves them dwindling in a brutal world. The real world of Kafka’s *Metamorphosis* acknowledges and accepts the happenings of the unreal world. Hence, the real world approves and affirms the existence of the fictitious world. When Gregor Samsa transforms into an insect, he is at first surprised however, he later ends up accepting his condition. Similarly, his family sees his transformation more as a tragedy than absurdity. They never question the absurdity of this bizarre event instead, they are saddened at this misfortune.

Perpetual domination of arbitrary power:

The tragedy of the 20th century industrial age and complex systems of administration have an irreversible impact on our lives. Kafka’s story describes the struggle between arbitrary power and the common people caught up in them. This soul-crushing power lies in the hands of a capitalist system that serves itself. It is a bureaucratic system that exists solely to perpetuate itself instead of serving justice. Most of the time, the protagonist of a Kafka novel is an office worker who struggles to fight through obstacles to reach their goal. However, this agony of struggle ends up being extremely irrational and complicated hence, making success seem futile in the first place.

Kafka uses dream logic to unravel the brutal relationship between a tyrant authority and the individuals working for them. Politicians, aristocrats, judges and industrialists are the pioneers of this tyrant authority with an aim to establish a submissive workforce. Likewise, Gregor seems to be struggling in the face of a tyrant workplace where employees aren’t trusted. He is seen denouncing this tyranny, “What a fate, to be condemned to work for a firm where the smallest omission at once gave rise to the gravest suspicion! Were all employees in a body nothing but scoundrels, was there not among them one single loyal devoted man, who, though he might have wasted an hour or so of the firm’s time in a morning, was so tormented by conscience as to be driven out of his mind and actually incapable of leaving his bed?”

Kafka's strange solidarity with the working class is a result of his tumultuous and dominated relationship with his father. His father's disappointment in him became a crucial and painful part of his identity. Therefore, Kafka tries to break free from this tyrannical section of his life. Hence, in *The Metamorphosis*, Gregor Samsa's ultimate escape from his suffering was death. This is symbolical of Kafka's own perspective towards his life. Franz Kafka sees death as his only way out from his father's domineering attitude. Kafka could resonate with the weak and victims because it resembled his relationship with his father. In this relationship, he was the victim and his father was the abuser. His father abused his power over Kafka to constantly subject him to scrutiny and ill-treatment. Thus, the vicious relationship of domination and power became the soul of his work. He symbolically analysed the psychological structure between the domination and the dominated through his writings. For example- In *The Metamorphosis*, Gregor Samsa is financially abused by his family. Later on, he is severely mistreated by his father. Gregor Samsa has been the dominated even before his transformation however, he fails to notice this dominance until the very end.

The existentialist philosophy in Kafka's work:

In his work Existentialism is a Humanism Jean-Paul Sartre believes, "the first effect of existentialism is that he puts every man in possession of himself as he is, and places the entire responsibility for his existence squarely upon his own shoulders". (Paul-Sartre, 1946). The protagonists of Kafka's novels are the only solution to their problems however, they choose to follow the perpetual cycle of self-disgust and oppression. The choice of becoming the sole earner of the family was Gregor's, a choice that punished him instead of rewarding him.

We have to take responsibility for all our actions. "man is condemned to be free. Condemned, because he did not create himself, yet is nevertheless at liberty, and from the moment that he is thrown into this world he is responsible for everything he does". Therefore, there is a constant struggle for survival in an intricate web of obstacles in this world. And man finds himself to be at the center of this web, surviving in a world that he has no control over. However, what he does have control over is himself. A man is defined by his actions which makes him in charge of his own destiny. Man is given both power and freedom at the same time.

Humans suffer from a rigid desire for a purpose and an escape from the suffering and absurdity of everyday life. We have no control over the source of our problems and we fail to produce effective ways to solve them. There is a constant struggle to find solace and acceptance. Nonetheless, we continue to fight the absurdity in our lives as rational beings but this only seems to self-perpetuate the very struggle we are trying to eliminate. Kafka directly confronts the suffering of the self instead of using fabricated lies to give false hope to the soul.

Kafka uses the element of absurd in his novel to reveal our flaws in front of us. In this way, he reminds us of our freedom of choice. This freedom of choice allows us to change the world we live in. We are both the problem and the solution. Therefore, *The Metamorphosis* focuses on the seemingly ceaseless problems of man and his attempt to stand up for himself in front of convoluted systems of government. In Kafka's work, man is in pursuit of an unattainable goal which makes his journey useless. The notion of absurdity and hopelessness in his work is emblematic of the existential philosophy of life.

Kafka uses his writing to confront the absurd which leads to a conflict. The character's effort to make sense of the world around them in this conflict remains futile. No matter how hard the protagonist tries, success remains unattainable. In fact, by the end of the story, success almost becomes pointless, leaving the character to wait for the last resort i.e., death. Similarly, after seeing no way out of his unexplainable metamorphosis, Gregor Samsa is mistreated by his family to the point where he prays for his own death.

Another notion of Kafkaesque refers to the complicated and perpetual cycle of government systems that entraps individuals. These individuals are lost in this constant cycle of exploitation in the hands of capitalist systems. Gregor Samsa is seen worrying about reaching his workplace on time despite turning into an insect. His attempts to survive in a competitive and pushy environment has left him obsessed with work and money. On top of that, he is struggling under the weight of his family's expectations and demands. A young man has taken the sole responsibility of paying off his parents' debt, providing for his family as well as looking out for his sister's education. Although Gregor Samsa hates his boss and his job as a commercial traveller, he is unable to fight for his own ambitions. His urge to fulfil his responsibilities of taking care of his family has overpowered his inner desire to liberate himself from societal expectations. Kafka uses the elements of disorienting and surreal writing style to criticise the selfish and illogical demands of society and family.

The sense of guilt over ego:

Gregor is struggling between his inner needs and his urge to fulfil his responsibilities. On one hand, his unconscious mind wants him to quit his job and escape the social order he dislikes. On the other hand, his conscious mind wants him to rise to the expectations of being the sole earner of his family. However, his metamorphosis gives him the reason to follow his inner conscience but it still doesn't stop Gregor from feeling guilty and anxious. At last, Gregor's guilt overpowers his ego, leading him to realise that the best thing to happen would be his death. This notion of being ashamed of our inner urges to the point where we wish for our own death is the very crux of Kafkaesque philosophy.

Franz Kafka discloses the real and unreal realms of his life in his work. Kafka's works reveal that part of his mind to us which is terrified of arbitrary judgement yet strongly desires to strive towards freedom. As the protagonist strives towards freedom, he is bound by other restrictions leading him to finally pray for his death. In the novel, Gregor is treated poorly by his own family to the point where his existence is a burden to them. He goes from being the sole provider of his family to being an obligation in their path to freedom. Ultimately, he begins to see himself as the "vermin" he is under the crushing weight of guilt and expectations. Kafka is not just an influential writer in German Literary History but is also that hidden and ashamed part of us all. A part that is wrecked by a constant feeling of self-disgust under the obligation of social parameters and responsibility.

The very first idea of existentialism gives the responsibility of our livelihood to us. This gives us power while at the same time, takes away our freedom. In fact, Jean-Paul Sartre says in his Existentialism is a Humanism, "The first effect of existentialism is that it puts every man in possession of himself as he is, and places the entire responsibility for his existence squarely upon his own shoulders. And, when we say that man is responsible for himself, we do not mean that he is responsible only for his own individuality, but that he is responsible for all men". (Paul-Sartre, 1946). Man's action has both consequences and influence on the rest of mankind. Western literature often contains this notion of guilt which comes from the Original Sin in the Bible. It was Adam and Eve who ate the forbidden fruit yet the whole of humankind carries this guilt. Similarly, Gregor's guilt is the result of his inexplicable and uncontrollable metamorphosis. Gregor is facing the crisis of choosing between responsibility and freedom. On one hand, he feels obligated to the demands imposed on him by societal orders and his family and on the other, he sees a way out of this trap. Gregor's metamorphosis becomes the reason for his escape from the toxic and manipulative trap of social obligations.

Alienation in *The Metamorphosis*:

The most tragic form of alienation that man suffers from is his own needs. Gregor Samsa is alienated from his deepest desires due to the overpowering guilt of his outer self. He sees it as his responsibility to pay off his parents' debt and look after their livelihood. The morning of his metamorphosis, the first thought that comes to Gregor Samsa's mind is the odiousness of his job. "O God, he thought, what an exhausting job I've picked on! Travelling about day in, day out. It's much more irritating work than doing the actual business in the warehouse, and on top of that there's the trouble of constant travelling, of worrying about train connexions, the bed and irregular meals, casual acquaintances that are always new and never become intimate friends. The devil take it all!" Gregor is uncomfortable in his job however, the weight of expectations and responsibilities has made him cloak his own needs. In the whirlwind of exhausting train rides and unhealthy amounts of workload, he has repressed his desire to quit his job. Gregor uses frivolous calculations to console himself.

Gregor talks about being “sacked on the spot” by his chief if he tries to get him to change his morning timings. “Let me just try that on with my chief; I’d be sacked on the spot. Anyhow, that might be quite a good thing for me, who can tell? If I didn’t have to hold my hand because of my parents I’d have given notice long ago, I’d have gone to the chief and told him exactly what I think of him. That would knock him endways from his desk!” Hence, Gregor clearly wants to quit his job because of his intolerable boss and the demanding atmosphere of his business firm. But, he has to hold back his inner urges for the sake of his family. He is seen hoping for his future, “Well, there’s still hope; once I’ve saved enough money to pay back my parents’ debts to him- that should take another five or six years- I’ll do it without fail”. Gregor decides to wait for another five or six years to quit his job and discover his true desires. He expects himself to someday, take charge and determine his purpose in life. However, Gregor does not know anything about this so-called future he will cut himself loose for. Thus, Kafka gives him the role of a creature that is alien to him the same way his desires are.

Moreover, Gregor goes from being the breadwinner of his family to being a sight of shame. After Gregor’s metamorphosis, his family is unable to even look at him. Gregor’s family is so frightened of his physical form that they end up isolating him. Gregor finally manages to see himself from his family’s perspective, as a matter of shame, disgust and fear. He becomes worthless in their eyes as contrary to how much they respected and valued him earlier. Gregor’s selfless love for his family also becomes the reason behind his alienation because he is only viewed as the breadwinner of the family and nothing more. For them, his existence is limited and never exceeds being anything other than a breadwinner.

Conclusion:

Kafka’s work is emblematic of the inevitable idea of an existential crisis looming on the human race. He has very accurately portrayed the suffering of the human race in his writings. The confining dominion of the social structure which imprisons even the most intellectual of us all is symbolical in his fiction. Moreover, he embarks on the condition of man in the age of industrialisation where he is constantly abused and dominated. In the manipulative cycle of authoritative systems, the working class is exploited which Kafka demonstrates in his works. He has successfully demolished the line between art and life since his real and fictional life is so thoroughly intertwined. His writings are so relatable that even in the 21st century, people can relate to the feeling of alienation, profoundly found in his stories. Gregor Samsa suffers from the loss of purpose as his sole responsibility as the breadwinner of the family is taken from him, leaving him desperate for the meaning of life after his transformation. The only way out of this transcendental puzzle for Gregor Samsa is to die. The importance of freedom and individuality in a bureaucratic society is also a focus here. Gregor’s lack of individuality led to his death. Since Gregor considers his responsibility to be the sole provider of the house, he fails to draw a line between family expectations and his personal desires. This leads to a complete loss of self, especially after his metamorphosis. Franz Kafka has successfully portrayed the events which follow after the loss of individuality. Once Gregor Samsa lost his sense of individualism, he is reduced to an “it”. “It” is

merely a thing instead of a human being in both physical as well as psychological state. In the end, Gregor Samsa is seen and treated as a 'thing' because he has lost what made him a person. He lost his individualism.

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